

Bread, Games, and Silence: How Sports Distract from Crisis in Morocco

Thesis: Sports in Morocco are used as a tool of distraction and passive control

The volumes are at their maxes, united cheers, frustration, and hope across everybody's face. Cafe's seats booked weeks in advance, not a chair in sight, and everyone is hooked on the same ball for hours; no one dares to move. This scene is the same in the whole country; all the differences disappear at this moment, age, gender, origins, and beliefs, once held important, a judge of character becomes forgotten in the heat of the match.

Such scene may represent the beauty of the Moroccan sport culture, a strong unity throughout the whole country, and yet, even this beautiful landscape is touched by the reality of the world; everything has its good and bad.

Football no longer serves as entertainment but rather as a distraction. While the match itself only goes for 2 hours, it stays on people's minds for weeks. Cafe's discussion, newspapers, TV shows, news articles, everything goes around that two hours, thus becoming way longer to be just entertainment. This focus doesn't leave much room to real-world problems and events, so they go unnoticed by the majority, undiscussed, unbothered, until they become a reality harder to solve, lived with. When the buzz of the match starts going down, some light hits what was left long uncovered, only then do they start complaining, until the next match.

This cycle didn't start yesterday, and unfortunately, nothing seems to insinuate a close ending to it.

A match, for the Moroccan public, is more than just an entertainment or a quality time with friends and family; it's an escape. The people sympathize with their team; if they're winning, pride and joy are on everybody's face as if the win is personally theirs, and if losing, anger, disappointment, and frustration as if the loss touches them negatively.

They would scream at the players instructions, reproach them for their mistakes, and may take credit for knowing that the player will score the goal and how. The players here represent them in real life, what they would and wanted to do, and all the success that they are dreaming of.

An anger toward the referee over an injustice or an overreacted punishment, the representation of what they may have kept for a similar situation in the real world, it may be something small, his boss, but it's mostly something greater, unfair prices, lacking medical options, stressful environment... The repressed reaction to all of these factors gets to be voiced by judging, insulting, and criticizing the referee because there are no consequences attached to such action, in contrast to doing the same to the real source of the problems, which probably won't be held as gently; it may finish in serious punishment.

“The football mindset” is also something that I’ve been noticing too, mostly in teenagers and children, when Morocco has finally achieved real success in education, (The Global Economy (organization), 2022) The numbers may seem low compared to other countries but for a country relatively recently out of colonialization and the number from 20 years ago, there has been a lot of improvement thanks to the king Mohammed VI, may God protect him by founding **Mohammed VI Foundation for the Promotion of Social Works of Education and Training** and the laws to ensure the education of kids under 15. This growth is at rest of decay because of the mindset kids these days are adopting, seeing the success our national team and their players had these past years, and at the World Cup, they see football as a promising route, thus ditching education for it, a lot of dropouts or failed classes for training. Their motto is “ it doesn't come with the pen, it will come with the foot ”, a pretty catchy phrase in the Moroccan dialect, bearer to promises it can never keep. The reality that these kids don't know or that their hopes hide is that the success of such competitive sport is minimal, the player they look up to, Moroccan in origin and nationality, most grew up in Europe, played next to world-renowned teams, so got noticed, an environment that couldn't be more different from theirs. Indeed, their dream is not impossible, but even while having all the talent, the discipline needed to be a top-notch footballer, sadly does not only ensure success but also a career, a job, and sacrificing education for football is surely not the best decision. Football can be a hobby that you develop and maybe pursue with passion, and education as a kid should be your full-time job. Many footballers have degrees and a successful career because they, too, understand how unstable football is. The rise of the football dream will bring the downfall of many, dropouts will be seen as a route, unemployment as pursuing a passion...and failure will no longer sting, as long as it's draped in a jersey and false hope.

Priorities have been defined around football, for a country like Morocco with almost **€100.5 billion** in debt, accounting for **70 percent of GDP**, a very lacking health department with **0.7 hospital beds per 1,000 inhabitants** (Worlddata.info (organization), 2025)² or **936 inhabitants per hospital bed** (The inhabitant-to-hospital-bed ratio varies by region in Morocco (Zahidi & Ahmed, 2022), in comparison the average hospital beds per 1000 people is around 4.6 (British Medical Association (organization), 2024), and a huge regional disparity, **897 inhabitants per physician** in **Csablanca Settat** while a **3396 inhabitant per physicist** in **Draa tafilalt**, with regional ratios varying from **693 to 2,330 inhabitants per bed and 30%** of the rural population lives more than **10 km** from any health facility with a really bad infrastructure. These regional disparities are not only in medicine but also in education. Only **39.9% of rural women** are literate, compared to **69.9% in urban areas** (2022) and more. In infrastructure, Rural internet access trails urban areas (~70% vs. ~95%), impacting education, civic engagement, and economic inclusion (German Council on Foreign Relations (DGAP), 2024)

And a huge difference in Human Development Index, Casablanca–Rabat region HDI **0.734**, while Southern regions (e.g. Souss-Massa) HDI **0.681** (Wikipedia contributors, 2025) Not only that, but people lack pure essentials; Morocco has a huge medicine shortage (Madiha, 2025). Around **20% of rural health centers** report frequent **stock-outs of essential medicines** like insulin and antibiotics (Boutakrint, 2024). And when patients do find treatment, the financial cost is usually more than they can afford, treating chronic diseases such as diabetes, hypertension, and cancer has been rising at **~12% per year**, often outpacing average

household income growth and **nearly 30% of Moroccan citizens still lack health insurance**, limiting public access to essential medicine reimbursement (El Morabet, 2021) and more challenges (OECD (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development), 2024) All of these limitations and disparities are being looked at, they are known and there have been multiple attempt to solve them, they invested more but it wasn't enough, if that's all they ae trying their best but while the people are suffering, Morocco invested and will invest **€3.95 billion**, these investment will monderinaise infrastructure and transportation but only for the big cities where tourists will be in the wordcup enlarging further more the gap between rural and urban cities, not only that but the huge stadiums, we're talking about **€5.4 billion** in building and restoring stadiums (Hespress, 2024) like **stadium hassan 2** that will be a pride as the biggest stadium in the world only to become quite a burden after the worldcup, we've got no high notch league that can play there to make money, our average stadium now doesnt always sold out and what team can oplay there one the world cup finishes, some town club? Morocco invested **€5.4 billion** in building and restoring stadiums but only **2.3 billion** in education, that billion is in Dh, investment in education is only **€219 million** that's primary, middle&highschools as well as universities all across the country, **€1.24 billion** in medicine while people can't find or afford essential medicine for blood pressure, kidney... and in rural region not event insulin and antibiotics or a healthcare of any kind, **€284.5 million** in Water Infrastructure and some rural regions aren't even connected to drinkable water,... (Lindbergh, 2025) The money invested in stadiums we will only use during the World Cup should be used for people who need basic amenities. Growth should first be visible on moroccans first, before trying to race for the biggest stadium in the world award. I do understand that these investment would boost tourism but the touristic sector in morocco is unstructured, that's why it's always estimated, as a state, Morocco only gains money through taxes in the touristic sector from transportation and hotels only, rented appartements and cars, restaurants, cafes, bazaars,... that's money that the state is losing and that people isnt beneficieng from. This is the first problem that should be solved before investing that type of money into stadiums, and even then, it's still a lot.

The distraction that sports make has always been made to some parts' favor. In Morocco, it only started at colinisation, football been made as a tool of control, as Étienne de La Boétie (1549) said "Plays, farces, spectacles ... these were ... the instruments of tyranny. By these ... the ... dictators ... lulled their subjects under the yoke ..." the french colonisation has used sports as a way to distract the people for years, sure they're have been resistors but not enough of them to end the colinisation. The French colonial saw sport as "soft power, a power with no weapons that goes unnoticed until already too late, one that had seemed in Morocco's favor til the light had finally hit the damage.

During their colonization, the French managed to take a lot of Morocco's natural resources, control the Moroccan market, its financial transactions, and drown it in debts with high interest. It's true that Morocco was weak during that time, but even in the start, there were a lot of strong resistors, some won battles until the movement died. The people were distracted after the French founded clubs and organized tournaments, all designed to occupy strong, fit male audiences who would otherwise join nationalist resistors.

(RSSSF (Rec.Sport.Soccer Statistics Foundation), 2025)

And this type of distraction is still being used now. Like the rest of the world, Morocco has also hit a rough patch after the quarantine, where companies tried to make back the profit they lost during it, and the start of the Ukrainian war, gas prices hit the roof. Prices in Morocco, naturally, increased, but they increased a little more than needed, and even after things had gone relatively back to normal, prices never really went back to their original price to keep up a better margin of profit. But how did they bring the news of the increases to people who suffered from cut salaries for more than six months, inflation, and general poor mental health after such a long lockdown? While the Moroccan national team reached new records in the World Cup, the first Arab team to reach the quarter final, the first African and Arab team to reach the semi-finals, it was also at the same time, at the end of November first time, the gas price reached 16 DH, Morocco became 5 first countries with the highest gasoline rates, a drop has indeed been noticed, but the companies did time their increases with the matches then and now too. The nearest article to that date is this one: (Morocco World News, 2022). In October, before the price of gas reached 16 DH, which proves what I said earlier: our focus always shifts to football in critical times. The increase in the price of transportation for this food led to protests against the minister, who owns one of the biggest fuel companies in Morocco, to not only find a solution but also to resign. (Lamine, 2022) But this died with the start of the World Cup, even when a huge segment of society couldn't find food and relied on donations. These are things seen but unspoken of during that time because the first thing that came up whenever we talked was the match: "Did you see the score?" What a goal..." their worries and problems once again forgotten for the joy and pride they felt talking about it.

In both of these situations, you can't blame the people without understanding their situation first. Football was an escape, when they were unjustly treated, suffering, hungry, miserable, when the drought years came in succession, when not only was food expensive but scarce, when they were robbed in daylight but couldn't budge without getting killed and harm their family, when the prices only went up and those who talked were sent to prison. It's true that there are countries far more off than Morocco; it's true that most of those who were sent to jail wrongly by the government always get forgiven by the king; the most unfortunate may indeed find help from those fortunate. But that doesn't mean it's easy, that doesn't mean it's survivable, so you can't blame people who escape into a good memory, the only good memory, and hold it tight. This isn't a research paper to blame the Moroccan people on their current and past situations for their distraction it's a paper to make them aware, and many more that entertainment has and always had been to distract as Plato's said "People are like prisoners watching shadows on a cave wall, mistaking appearances for the truth, while the real world remains unseen." It may look to the world and us during the World Cup that we were thriving, but most people then lived day by day, whatever their sidehustles managed to offer them. Football, like any entertainment, is good to watch, forget the stress during it, but only during it shouldn't occupy you more than the two hours it lasts so you wouldn't become an easy prey to those who await your distraction.

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